

This project 20NRM02 MFMET has received funding from the EMPIR program co-financed by the Participating States and from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program.

20NRM02 MFMET

D3: 'Calibration guide for the evaluation of flow-related quantities in microfluidic devices including an example of 3 industrial applications submitted to EURAMET for approval publication' (A2.2.5)

Work package 2

Lead partner of the deliverable: RISE Research Institutes of Sweden AB (RISE)

Due date of the deliverable: 30 June 2023

Actual submission date: 11 September 2023

<https://mfmet.eu>

This report was written as part of activity A2.2.5 from the EMPIR Establishing Metrology Standards in Microfluidic Devices (MFMET) project. The three-year European project commenced on 1st June 2021 and focused on providing a generic methodology of accurate measurement of a particular quantity in a microfluidic device by utilising standardised methods and reference documents, e.g. VIM & GUM. For more details about this project, please visit <https://mfmet.eu>

This report was written by:

Name	Institution	E-mail
Oliver Bker	RISE	oliver.buker@ri.se
Mikkel Copeland	DTI	mico@dti.dk
Thomas Schrder Daugbjerg	DTI	tsda@teknologisk.dk
Florestan Ogheard	CETIAT	florestan.ogheard@cetiat.fr
Kevin Romieu	CETIAT	kevin.romieu@cetiat.fr
Elsa Batista	IPQ	ebatista@ipq.pt
Vania Silverio	INESC MN	vania.silverio@tecnico.ulisboa.pt
Başak Akselli	TBİTAK	basak.akselli@tubitak.gov.tr
Jan Gerřl	CMI	jgersl@cmi.cz
Sabrina Kartmann	HSG IMIT	sabrina.kartmann@hahn-schickard.de
Joost Lotters	BHT	J.C.Lotters@bronkhorst.com

EMPIR

The EMPIR initiative is co-funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme and the EMPIR Participating States

Contents

1	Scope.....	3
2	Survey of flow-related metrology needs of the microfluidics industry	3
2.1	Flow quantities.....	4
2.2	Liquid properties	4
3	Measurement of flow quantities	5
3.1	Flow rate (static, dynamic).....	5
3.2	Flow resistivity/resistance vs flow rate.....	14
3.3	Internal volume.....	19
4	Example of 3 industrial applications	19
4.1	TOPAS microfluidic chip	19
4.1.1	Flow rate determined 'outside' the chip at IPQ.....	21
4.1.2	Flow resistivity determined at CETIAT	23
4.1.3	Internal volume determination at IPQ.....	24
4.2	PDMS microfluidic chip	25
4.2.1	Flow rate determined 'outside' the chip at IPQ.....	25
4.2.2	Internal volume determination at IPQ.....	26
4.3	Microfluidic pump.....	26
4.3.1	Flow rate determined at IPQ.....	27
5	References	28

1 Scope

This document will act as a calibration guide on the evaluation of flow quantities in microfluidic devices. In this guide, the measurement methods for the most important flow quantities in the microflow range are explained in more detail. Finally, three selected examples will show how this guide can be implemented and how such measurements are carried out for microfluidic components.

Activity number	Activity description	Partners (Lead in bold)
A2.2.5 M25	<p>Using input from A2.1.3 and A2.2.1-A2.2.4, RISE with support from INESC MN, DTI, CETIAT, IPQ, CMI, HSG IMIT, BHT and TUBITAK will write a calibration guide on the evaluation of flow quantities in microfluidic devices including an example of 3 industrial applications. RISE will submit this to EURAMET for publication.</p> <p>Once agreed by the consortium, the coordinator on behalf of RISE, INESC MN, DTI, CETIAT, IPQ, CMI, TUBITAK, BHT and HSG IMIT submit the guide to EURAMET as D3: 'Calibration guide for the evaluation of flow-related quantities in microfluidic devices including an example of 3 industrial applications submitted to EURAMET for approval publication'.</p> <p>This EURAMET guide will be used as guidelines for NMI/DIs wishing to introduce new calibration services such as in-channel flow rate and velocity, and in-channel liquid (droplet) volume.</p>	RISE , INESC MN, DTI, CETIAT, IPQ, CMI, TUBITAK, HSG IMIT, BHT

2 Survey of flow-related metrology needs of the microfluidics industry

An inventory was compiled based on interviews with Microfluidics industrial experts, the results of the interview are available on <https://mfmet.eu>.

The priorities identified by industry experts for measurements during manufacturing of microfluidic devices and components are listed in order of importance:

1. Factors affecting pressure drop [1] and flow resistance in the device (e.g. wettability or deviation from ideal dimensions);
2. Factors affecting the bonding quality of polymeric components (glass transition temperature, melting temperature, molecular weight number and distribution, etc.);
3. Leakage, burst pressure and maximum working pressure;
4. Consensus on the information of materials used, such as optical transmission, autofluorescence of polymeric materials, thickness of glass substrates, etc.

Other topics of interest are:

- Measurement of rapidly changing flow rates.
- Verification of biological viability after dispensing biomaterial on chip / in device.

From this survey, two categories (flow quantities and liquid properties) were identified.

2.1 Flow quantities

The flow quantities are presented in order of priority:

1. Flow rate (static, dynamic)
2. Flow resistivity/resistance vs flow rate (Reynolds (Re) numbers, drag force)
3. Internal volume
4. Dead volume
5. Droplet size/volume variation
6. Flow pressure (inline pressure)

Note: Leakage rate (non-destructive/non-intrusive and fast test – use pressure drop with air; air/liquid ratio) is dealt within Work Package 1 of this project.

2.2 Liquid properties

The liquid properties are presented according to priority:

1. Viscosity
2. Density
3. Contact angle
4. Refractive index (optical methods)

Note: Surface tension and wettability are dealt within Work Package 3 of this project.

In the context of this work, a comprehensive literature review was conducted regarding normative flow property standards and terminology in the field of microflow. The report, A2.2.1: “A literature review of existing metrology and normative standards related to the flow properties and microfluidic devices”, can be found on the project’s website <https://mfmet.eu>.

This report, Deliverable D3, deriving from activity A2.2.5, presents in more detail the measurement methods for the 3 most important topics of the “flow quantities” mentioned above. The “liquid properties” mentioned in section 2.2, will be discussed more extensively in report Deliverable D4 from A2.3.5.

This report includes the compilation of results already found elsewhere (<https://mfmet.eu> & <https://zenodo.org/communities/mfmet>)

- 1.) A2.1.3: Inventory and prioritization of flow-related metrology needs of the microfluidics industry;
- 2.) [A2.2.1: A literature review of existing metrology and normative standards related to the flow properties and microfluidic devices](#);
- 3.) [A2.2.2: Development of test protocols for microfluidic devices](#);
- 4.) A2.2.3: Documented example of the test protocol for flow resistivity, flow rate and volume.

3 Measurement of flow quantities

3.1 Flow rate (static, dynamic)

There are various methods for determining the flow rate, e.g. gravimetric method, front tracking, displacement methods (piston prover as flow generator, interferometer method), μ PIV and others. In addition, there are also secondary methods (e.g. flow meters) which are not included in this report.

In the following, the gravimetric method will be presented in more detail, which is suitable for static and dynamic measurement of the flow rate.

Gravimetric method

The gravimetric method is used to determine a delivered mass of a liquid over a time interval. The method can be used on measurements for both inline flow sensors and flow generators. To achieve the measurements a weighing vessel, placed on a balance, collects the liquid to determine the mass delivered. While the delivery time interval for the collection of the mass is determined as well.

Flow describes the unit quantity delivered over a unit time. Fluid flow related to the gravimetric method consists of mass flow rate $\left[\frac{kg}{s}\right]$ and volume flow rate $\left[\frac{m^3}{s}\right]$. The mass flow rate relates the delivered mass to the delivery time and the volume flow rate relates the delivered mass in the mass flow rate to the delivered volume presented in Eq. 1 and Eq. 2 respectively:

$$q_m = \frac{m}{t} = \frac{m_1 - m_0}{t} \left(\frac{1 - \frac{\rho_a}{\rho_p}}{1 - \frac{\rho_a}{\rho_w}} \right) \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

$$q_V = \frac{q_m}{\rho_w t} = \frac{m_1 - m_0}{\rho_w t} \left(\frac{1 - \frac{\rho_a}{\rho_p}}{1 - \frac{\rho_a}{\rho_w}} \right) \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

According to IEC60601-2-24 [2], AAMI TIR 101 [3] and Bissig et al. [4] corrections for needle buoyancy, evaporation, and surface tension should be included, given by Eq. 3:

$$q_V = \frac{1}{t_f - t_i} \left[\left((I_L - I_E) \left(1 - \left(\frac{D_{tube}}{D_{tank}} \right)^2 \right) \right) \frac{1}{\rho_w - \rho_a} \left(1 - \frac{\rho_a}{\rho_p} \right) [1 - \gamma(T - 20)] \right] + \delta q_{evp} \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

Where:

q_m	Mass flow rate
q_v	Volume flow rate
m	Mass
t	Time
ρ_w	Density of liquid
ρ_a	Density of air
ρ_p	Density of standard weights

- t_i Start time
- t_f End time
- D_{tube} Outer diameter of the tube
- D_{tank} Inner diameter of the weighing vessel
- T Temperature

In a gravimetric microfluidic setup, an electronic balance is used (in most cases) to determine the delivered mass of a fluid from/through a test object (can be a flow generator or a flow meter). The time interval in which the mass is delivered is determined by a timing module to derive the mass flow rate. The climatic conditions such as air temperature, relative humidity and pressure are determined to correct for buoyancy effects on the balance in AAMI TIR 101 [3] . The liquid temperature is determined to convert the mass flow rate into a volumetric flow rate, considering the density of the liquid used. Often a layer of oil is applied on top of the water surface in the weighing tank (beaker) to reduce evaporation, especially at low flow rates.

Figure 1 – Example of a measurement setup for the gravimetric method.

All instruments used should be calibrated by an ISO17025 accredited laboratory or at an NMI/DI.

Balance

The balance must have the capacity to measure the desired mass to deliver, depended on flow rate, required stability time, calibration time, and repetitions. The resolution and actuating resolution of the balance must correspond to the desired flow rate to be measured.

Timing module

The timing module delivers a known accuracy of time synchronization related to the measured mass growth. Narrow calibration window places higher demands on the timing equipment.

Weighing vessel

As for the balance, select the weighing vessel to manage the amount of liquid dispensed during an entire calibration sequence, considering pre-fill, flow rate, stabilization time etc.

Thermometer and ambient conditions

The thermometer is utilized for the liquid temperature measurements to determine the density of the liquid. Where the ambient conditions are applied to determine stability of the ambient conditions and air density.

Calibration liquid

According to ISO 3696 [5] , the test solution should be either 0,9% normal saline water or distilled water of minimum grade 3. If clinically relevant liquids or other liquids relevant to microfluidic applications are used, the cause and impact must be carefully considered.

When performing the gravimetric method, there are a few important issues that should be considered.

Weighing vessel and needle

The weighing vessel placed on the balance, to collect the liquid, must have well known and uniform dimensions since these have impact on the uncertainty contribution of needle buoyancy effect. The weighing vessel and needle must be clean to avoid undesired changes in surface tension and needle roughness.

Stabilization time

The system requires time to settle and then stabilize after introducing a flow rate. To reduce the measurement fluctuations, it is necessary to exceed well past the settling time for the system, typically, 95% of the set flow rate must be reached before starting the measurements.

Liquid and ambient condition stability

The stability of both the liquid and the ambient conditions has large impact on microfluidic measurements. Therefore, they must be reduced as much as possible.

Evaporation

The amount of evaporation from the surface of the liquid can affect the measurements, making the flow appear lower than it really is. Therefore, it must be considered by either correcting for or reducing the evaporation, using for example an evaporation trap or an oil layer on top of the weighted liquid.

Degasification

If the calibration liquid does contain dissolved gas, it may cause measurement issues. Typically, the calibration liquid is degassed prior to calibration or inline during the calibration. Degasification can be performed using a commercial degasser, which is composed of a vacuum pump and a permeation membrane.

A. Uncertainty budget

The main standard uncertainties considered in a gravimetric setup are: mass measurements (m), density of the mass pieces (ρ_B), density of the water (ρ_W), density of the air (ρ_A), evaporation rate (δQ_{evap}), water temperature (T), time (t), expansion coefficient (γ), standard deviation of the measurements (δQ_{rep}) and buoyancy on the immersed dispensing needle (δQ_{mbuoy}) [6]

Table 1 – Uncertainty budget of the gravimetric facility at IPQ for a flow rate of around 1 ml/h.

Uncertainty components $u(x_i)$		$u(x_i)$	Distribution	Evaluation	c_i	$(c_i x_i)^2$	ν_{eff}
$u(m_{ind,f})$	Final mass (g)	2,86E-05	Normal	B	1,06E-03	3,02927E-08	50000
$u(\rho_{w,b})$	Density of the water (g/ml)	6,21E-04	Rectangular	B	-2,60E-04	1,61314E-07	50
$u(\rho_a)$	Density of the air (g/ml)	2,89E-06	Rectangular	B	2,28E-04	6,56797E-10	50000
$u(\rho_c)$	Density of the mass pieces (g/ml)	2,50E-03	Normal	B	4,79E-09	1,19675E-11	50
$u(T)$	Temperature (°C)	7,02E-01	Normal	B	-2,59E-09	1,81839E-09	50
$u(\gamma_s)$	Expansion coefficient (/°C)	2,89E-07	Rectangular	B	-5,94E-04	1,71591E-10	50000
$u(m_{ind,i})$	Initial mass (g)	2,86E-05	Normal	B	-1,06E-03	3,02926E-08	50000
$u(Q_{Evap})$	Evaporation (g/ml)	1,47E-08	Rectangular	B	1,00E+00	1,46693E-08	50000
$u(t_f)$	Final time (s)	7,00E-04	Normal	B	2,74E-07	1,91629E-10	50
$u(t_i)$	Initial time (s)	7,00E-04	Normal	B	-2,74E-07	1,91629E-10	50
$u(\delta Q_{mbuoy})$ $\delta Q_{mbuoy} =$ $Q_w(d_i/d_b)^2$	Buoyancy (ml/s)	2,38193E-05	Normal	B	1,06E-03	2,52604E-08	50000
$u(\delta Q_{rep})$	Repeatability (ml/s)	1,22744E-06	Normal	A	1,00E+00	1,22744E-06	24
<i>Flow (ml/s)</i>	0,000259099						
<i>ν_{eff}</i>	24,91998211						
<i>k</i>	2,11						
<i>Expanded uncertainty (ml/s)</i>	2,61409E-06						
<i>Expanded uncertainty (%)</i>	1,01						

B. Test protocols

Preparation

Place all equipment in the room where the test is to be carried out at least 24 hours before starting the measurement.

Flushing the system

Dead volume in the system may cause entrapment of air and could compromise the integrity of the measurements. Therefore, the system must be flushed prior to calibration start up. Circulating the system with degassed liquid will in time absorb entrapped air. At low flow rates CO₂ and isopropanol alcohol (IPA) are recognized methods to flush air from fluid systems. When flushed, run the system continuously with the calibration liquid until no flushing media is left.

Calibration start-up

Carefully prepare a clean weighing vessel with enough liquid to insert the needle. During preparation no liquid must be present on the walls. Place the container on the balance.

Insert the needle into a liquid layer in the container. The needle must be well below the water surface inside the container. However, the flow that exits the needle must not be located too close to the vessel's floor, since the inertia of the liquid is in risk of exerting an undesired force on the balance.

Measure the temperature at the liquid source reservoir and set the flow rate.

During the calibration

When the stabilisation time is reached (typically when the flow rate remains within $\pm 5\%$ of its target value [3]), acquire mass, time, and ambient condition data continuously. Check the ambient conditions for fluctuations.

End of calibration

When the calibration time is reached stop the acquisition and determine the temperature of the liquid in the container.

The number of repetitions should be at least 3 per flow rate.

Front tracking method

The front tracking method for flow measurements [25] [26] is an optical method that consists of tracking the position of the meniscus of a liquid (liquid/air or liquid/liquid interface) inside a (typically) capillary tube over time. An optical image acquisition system and image processing software is used to achieve the position over time of the meniscus. Knowing the displacement of the meniscus over time and the cross-section area of the capillary, it is possible to calculate the flow rate. Alternatively, the front tracking method can be performed in a microfluidic channel if the inner dimensions of the channel are known along with their associated uncertainties.

The fluid flowrate related to the front tracking method relates the optically acquired velocity of the fluid $\left(\frac{x_2-x_1}{\Delta t}\right)$ to the dimensions of the capillary tube (πr^2) . If the flow is measured inside a channel, replace (πr^2) by the channel's cross-section.

$$q_v = \frac{x_2-x_1}{\Delta t} \pi r^2 \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

Where: x_i is the position of the meniscus in the direction of the flow, Δt is the time interval between the positions, and r is the capillary section radius.

The capillary tube's material expansion property as a function of temperature $[1 - \gamma (T - 20)]$ is included to take deviation of the dimensions into account.

$$q_v = \frac{x_2-x_1}{\Delta t} \pi r^2 [1 - \gamma (T - 20)] \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

Where:

- q_v Volume flow rate
- γ Capillary material coefficient of expansion
- T Calibration liquid temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)

Similarly, the liquid's thermal expansion during the measurement should be evaluated using equation (Eq. 5).

The test method relies on three stages: calibration of the camera (determining the pixel size), image processing, and determination of position of the meniscus.

- The calibration of the camera determines the relationship between dimensions of a known and calibrated object (for example the outer diameter of the capillary) and pixels of an image. Usually, the output of the camera's calibration is the pixel size in microns (μm).

Figure 2 – Camera calibration using capillary's outer diameter.

Figure 3 – Camera calibration using a standard (micrometre object from Olympus).

- Image processing facilitates the identification of contours which makes the meniscus available for accurate positioning. Image processing includes image segmentation, digital image correlation, correction for misalignment, etc.
- The determination of the position of the meniscus is identified by software tools able to find coordinates of the meniscus, either at reference point(s) along its contour or its average position along the flow direction. Meniscus positions are determined for each successive image. The meniscus velocity is calculated as the time derivative (global or on a defined sliding time window) of its successive timestamped positions.

Figure 4 – Determination of the position of the meniscus.

All the instruments used should be calibrated by an accredited laboratory or an NMI/DI.

A typical setup may include:

- Capillary tube (or any other tubing or channel of known dimensions with associated uncertainties)
- High resolution camera
- image processing software

Figure 5 – Example of a front tracking setup for micro and nano flow measurements and calibrations.

A. Uncertainty budget

The main standard uncertainties considered related to the front tracking method are: meniscus displacement, $u(\Delta x)$; time interval between frames, $u(t)$; capillary radius, $u(r)$; water temperature, $u(T_w)$; material expansion, $u(\gamma)$; stability, $u(\delta Q_{sta})$; standard deviation of the measurements $u(\delta Q_{rep})$ [7]

Table 2 – The estimated contribution for the front tracking method.

Uncertainty components	Estimation	$u(x_i)$	c_i	$(c_i x_i)^2$
Meniscus displacement (mm)	11,76	$1,50 \times 10^{-02}$	$2,35 \times 10^{-02}$	$1,25 \times 10^{-07}$
Radius (mm)	0,575	$1,47 \times 10^{-03}$	$9,63 \times 10^{-01}$	$2,01 \times 10^{-06}$
Time (s)	44,107	$2,97 \times 10^{-03}$	$-6,28 \times 10^{-03}$	$3,48 \times 10^{-10}$
Repeatability ($\mu\text{L/s}$)	0,0013	0,0013	1	$1,80 \times 10^{-06}$
Stability ($\mu\text{L/s}$)	$1,37 \times 10^{-04}$	$1,37 \times 10^{-04}$	1	$1,88 \times 10^{-08}$
Expansion coefficient ($1/^\circ\text{C}$)	0,00024	$6,92 \times 10^{-06}$	$-8,14 \times 10^{-01}$	$3,18 \times 10^{-11}$
Temperature ($^\circ\text{C}$)	22,94	0,005	$-2,77 \times 10^{-06}$	$1,92 \times 10^{-16}$
Flow rate ($\mu\text{L/h}$)	997,1	u_{comb} ($\mu\text{L/h}$)	7,2	
v_{eff}	100,15	k	2,02	
U_{exp} ($\mu\text{L/h}$)	15	U (%)	1,5	

B. Test protocols

Preparation

Place all equipment in the room where the test is to be carried out at least 24 hours before starting the measurement.

Flushing the system

Dead volume in the system may cause entrapment of air and could compromise the integrity of the measurements. Therefore, the system must be flushed prior to calibration start up. Circulating the system with degassed liquid will in time absorb entrapped air. At low flow rates CO₂ and isopropanol alcohol (IPA) are recognized methods to flush air from fluid systems. When flushed, run the system continuously with the calibration liquid until no flushing media is left.

Calibration start-up

Position the calibrated camera in front of the capillary's (or channel) section in which the meniscus will flow. Adjust the lighting, so that the image has the best contrast for the exposure time that will be used for the measurement. Make sure that the capillary is in focus and align it with the image bottom or top border so that it appears horizontal in the image.

Measure the temperature at the liquid source reservoir and set the flow rate.

During the calibration

When the stabilization time is reached (typically, if the flow rates remain at $\pm 5\%$ of its target value), acquire timestamped images, and ambient condition data continuously. Check the ambient conditions for fluctuations. If dynamic (fluctuating) flows are to be measured, make sure to choose a framerate sufficiently high (typically equal or superior to 1 frame per second - 1 fps).

End of calibration

When the calibration time is reached stop the image acquisition and ambient conditions recording.

Image processing & flow rate calculation

Apply image processing to determine the meniscus positions in each successive image and calculate the flow as the time derivative of the meniscus' positions.

The number of repetitions should be at least 3 per flow rate.

3.2 Flow resistivity/resistance vs flow rate

Flow resistivity measurement is used to determine the necessary pressure to achieve the desired flow through a microfluidic circuit, or conversely, to determine the flow rate corresponding to a given inlet pressure. Flow resistivity measurement consists of measuring the differential pressure (or solely the inlet pressure if the outlet is at atmospheric pressure) of a given microfluidic circuit and measuring the flow passing through the same microfluidic circuit, either simultaneously or sequentially, for at least one (preferably several) couple of flow rates and pressure. The output of this test can be a table of results and/or a graphical representation of 'flow rate vs pressure'. The flow resistivity can also be given in Pa·s/m³.

Flow resistance, also called hydrodynamic resistance or just microfluidic resistance, corresponds to the opposition that a fluidic element, like a pipe, offers to a flow through itself. Each element of a microfluidic circuit offers some resistance to the flow, which is translated into a pressure drop, which can be calculated by using the Hagen-Poiseuille equation:

$$\Delta P = QR_H \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

Where: ΔP is the pressure difference, or drop, between two points of the system, Q is the flow rate and R_H is the hydraulic resistance.

Under the assumptions stated below, it can be demonstrated that the pressure drop associated with a microchannel depends on the flow rate, the dimensions of the channel and the dynamic viscosity of the fluid itself. The flow resistor expressions for the most typical channel cross sections are as follows. These are, respectively: circle, rectangle, and square shapes:

$$R_{Hc} = \frac{8\mu L}{\pi r^4} \quad R_{H,rec} = \frac{12\mu L}{1-0,63\left(\frac{h}{w}\right)} \left(\frac{1}{h^3 w}\right) \quad R_{H,sq} = \frac{12\mu L}{1-0,917 \times 0,63} \left(\frac{1}{h^4}\right) \quad \text{Eq. 7}$$

Where:

- r Radius of the circle
- μ Dynamic viscosity
- L Length of the channel
- h Height of the channel
- w Width of the channel

The assumptions for this theoretical model are the following:

- Low Re number,
- Incompressible fluid,
- Unidirectional flow,
- Steady flow along the channel.
- Small fluid mass per distance unit, so gravity is negligible.
- Negligible surface tension forces
- Negligible friction forces from the wall of the channel

See Silverio & Cardoso [24] for a discussion of surface tension forces and friction forces from the wall of the channel. Their work explains that surface tension forces become increasingly dominant for smaller scales. Consequently, there is a scale too small for the above assumption of negligible surface tension forces to be valid, for example capillary devices. What is more, if the scale is too large the assumption of low Re number will be violated, for example macro scale pipes. It is worth noting that the description of pressure drop stated by Eq. 6 and Eq. 7 only is applicable for an intermediate range of scales for microchannels.

Measuring flow resistivity across a microfluidic device is performed using at least a pressure source (pressure controller in the figures below, which includes a pressure source an element uses to stabilize and control the pressure, such as a control valve), a flow sensor, and either:

- one pressure sensor at the device's inlet, the outlet being at atmospheric pressure, as shown in the following schematic:

Figure 6 – One pressure sensor.

- one differential pressure sensor in parallel of the microfluidic device, as shown in the following schematic:

Figure 7 – One differential sensor.

- two pressure sensors at inlet and outlet of the microfluidic device, as shown in the following schematic:

Figure 8 – Two pressure sensors.

In the three schematic drawings above, the specifications are:

Pressure controller

- It must be chosen according to the admissible pressure range in the microfluidic device. Generally, a pressure controller should be used between 10% and 100% of its pressure range capability.
- Minimum pressure at the outlet of the pressure controller is generally around 100 mbar in order to ensure good pressure control and stability.
- The stability of the pressure controller must be in accordance with the accuracy required for the pressure drop / flow resistivity measurement. This information can be found in the datasheet of the pressure controller. Note that the stability can be degraded due to the compliance (elasticity) of the entire setup and dead volumes which can entrap air (in case of a liquid as the test media).
- A sufficient pressure level at the pressure source (inlet) of the pressure controller should be provided in order to perform in a normal way. The minimum and maximum pressure level can be found in the datasheet of the pressure controller. The same apply for the required electrical power supply.
- The pressure controller should be at the same altitude as the microfluidic device.

Pressure sensor(s), differential pressure sensors

- It must be chosen according to the pressure range (or pressure drop range in case of a differential pressure sensor) to be measured in the microfluidic device. Generally, a pressure sensor should be used between 10% and 100% of its pressure range capability.
- The accuracy of the pressure sensor must be in accordance with the accuracy required for the pressure drop / flow resistivity measurement. This information can be found in the datasheet of the pressure sensor. Note that this accuracy can be degraded due to the compliance (elasticity) of the entire setup and dead volumes which can entrap air (in case of a liquid as the test media).
- The pressure sensor(s) should be at the same altitude as the microfluidic device.
- All pressure sensors should be calibrated before any pressure measurements. The calibration should be performed by a ISO17025:2017 accredited laboratory.
- In case of a liquid as the test media, the tubing connecting the pressure sensor(s) to the pressure controller and microfluidic device should be set downward so that air bubbles are expelled (purged) downstream of the setup.
- In case of a gas as the test media, the tubing connecting the pressure sensor(s) to the pressure controller and microfluidic device should be set upward so that liquid droplets (due for example to condensation of humidity) are expelled (purged) downstream of the setup.

Flow sensor

- It must be chosen according to the flow range to be measured in the microfluidic device. Generally, a flow sensor should be used between 10 % and 100 % of its pressure range capability.
- The accuracy of the flow sensor must be in accordance with the accuracy required for the pressure drop / flow resistivity measurement. This information can be found in the datasheet of the flow sensor. Note that this accuracy can be degraded due to the compliance (elasticity) of the entire setup and dead volumes which can entrap air (in case of a liquid as the test media).
- All flow sensors should be calibrated before any pressure measurements. The calibration should be performed by a ISO17025:2017 accredited laboratory.
- In the case of a liquid as the test medium, the tubing connecting the flow sensor(s) to the pressure controller and microfluidic device should be directed downwards so that any air bubbles are expelled (purged) downstream of the setup.
- In the case of a gas as the test medium, the tubing connecting the flow sensor(s) to the pressure controller and microfluidic device should be directed upwards so that liquid droplets (e.g. due to moisture condensation) are expelled (purged) downstream of the setup.

Fittings/connectors

- All fittings and connectors should be chosen and set keeping in mind that any leakage will cause measurement error and will degrade the flow resistivity accuracy.
- All fittings and connectors should be chosen as to minimize their dead volume.

Measurements should be performed in a temperature and humidity-controlled room. Temperature, ambient pressure, and humidity fluctuations range should be known, either by measurement (using calibrated sensors) or by knowledge of the control ranges, ensuring that the climate-control system (air-conditioning for example) is performing normally. Ideal conditions are $(23 \pm 2)^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $(55 \pm 5)\%$ HR.

All elements of the setup (pressure controller, measurements sensors, test media, and microfluidic devices) should be left in the room where the tests are to be performed at least 24 hours before the test, to ensure thermal equilibrium. Electrically powered elements such as the pressure controller and the pressure sensor(s) should be powered on at least 30 minutes before beginning any measurement. For pressure controllers requiring the filling of a reservoir, the latter should be filled beforehand, at least 30 minutes before beginning any measurement. The entire system, including pressure taps in case of differential pressure sensor, should be purged before beginning any measurement. Purge can be performed using the test media at the maximum admissible pressure of the pressure controller/pressure sensor(s)/microfluidic device (whichever has the lesser maximum admissible pressure).

A. Test protocol

1. Place of all setup elements in the room where the tests are to be performed, for at least 24 hours before beginning any measurement.
2. Connect all elements together to mount the setup, making sure that all fittings are tightly connected.
3. If necessary, fill the pressure controller reservoir at least 30 minutes before beginning any measurement.
4. Connect all required electrical power supplies to the pressure controller and pressure sensor(s), and power on at least 30 minutes before beginning any measurement.

5. Purge the setup using the test media at the maximum admissible pressure of the pressure controller/pressure sensor(s)/microfluidic device (whichever has the lesser maximum admissible pressure).
6. Zero the pressure and flow sensors to minimize any measurement offset.
7. Set a target pressure to the pressure controller and monitor the evolution of the pressure using the pressure sensor(s).
8. After reaching a stable pressure (not drifting upwards or downwards), record the measurement.
9. Repeat step 7 and 8 for all required target pressure.
10. In case of a differential pressure sensor or two pressure sensors, remove the microfluidic device and connect directly both pressure taps in order to measure the pressure drop. Repeat step 7 and 8 for all measured flows in the previous steps.
11. Calculate each flow resistivity according to Eq. 6. In case of a differential pressure sensor or two pressure sensors, subtract the pressure taps pressure drops to the calculated device's pressure drop.
12. An example of flow and pressure drop measurement is shown in the figure below, for four different flow and pressure measurements steps.

Figure 9 – Pressure drop and flow rate measurements.

Dry evaluation of flow resistivity

Dry calibration consists in using the dimensional measurement of the microfluidic device to calculate its flow resistivity. If possible, all needed dimensions should be measured using a ISO17025:2017 calibrated instruments with a measurement resolution and accuracy in agreement with the target measurement uncertainty.

Examples of dry evaluation of flow resistivity are given in:

<https://www.elveflow.com/microfluidic-reviews/general-microfluidics/flow-resistance/>

https://en.wikibooks.org/wiki/Microfluidics/Hydraulic_resistance_and_capacity

<https://www.elveflow.com/microfluidic-calculator>

3.3 Internal volume

The volume is determined gravimetrically by weighing the chip to be calibrated when empty and when filled with a suitable liquid. Each channel is tested separately. The difference obtained in the weighing measurements gives the mass of the liquid contained in a particular channel.

The tests using the gravimetric method for volume determination were performed the following conditions:

- a) Acclimatization time of 24 h, all the instruments and the water stood in the same room for 24 h;
- b) Controlled room temperature equal to (20 ± 3) °C;
- c) Room temperature variation during the measurements not more than 1 °C;
- d) Humidity room above 50%;
- e) Weight the empty and dry microchip;
- f) Measure the water temperature;
- g) Fill the microchip with water ensuring no bubbles are inside;
- h) Weight the chip full of water.

During the tests, the temperature of the water and the air, the relative humidity and the atmospheric pressure need to be continually measured and recorded. It should be noted that the placeholders for the plugs should remain dry. Only the channel inside should be filled with water.

4 Example of 3 industrial applications

In the following, it will be shown how this guide can be used by means of three specific examples of microfluidic components:

- A. Thermoplastic polymer (TOPAS) microfluidic chip
- B. Silicone polymer (PDMS, polydimethylsiloxane) microfluid chip
- C. Microfluidic pump (developed within the EMPIR 18 HLT08 MeDD2 project, task 3.2)

4.1 TOPAS microfluidic chip

At CETIAT a “Fluidic 157” microfluidic chip provided by Microfluidic ChipShop (<https://www.microfluidic-chipshop.com/catalogue/microfluidic-chips/polymer-chips/straight-channel-chips-microscopy-slide-format/straight-channel-chips-with-eight-parallel-channels-fluidic-157/>) with the following characteristics was investigated:

- Material: Topas (Topas is a COC – cyclic olefin copolymer – resin)
- 8 parallel channels of 100 µm width, 100 µm depth, 18 mm length
- 75,5 mm by 25,5 mm microscope slide format
- Luer fluidic interface, similar to “female mini luer port” integrated directly on the chip. Those ports can be found as “stand alone” ports, such as <https://darwin-microfluidics.com/products/stand-alone-female-mini-luer-ports-pack-of-10>

The following figure shows a schematic of the device under test (DUT).

Figure 10 – Schematic of the TOPAS “Fluidic 157” chip.

The following picture shows the DUT.

Figure 11 – TOPAS “fluidic 157” chip during testing.

IPQ performed the volume and flow measurements on two different chips provided by Microfluidic ChipShop:

Chip A - 16 parallel channels with fluid interface holes, Material: TOPAS® (polymer for medical use), Dimensions: 75,5 mm x 25,5 mm x 1,5 mm, model 10000198, lote (batch) Z1112070.

Figure 12 – TOPAS Chip A (IPQ).

Chip C - 16 parallel channels with mini luer fluidic interface, Material: TOPAS® (polymer for medical use), Dimensions: 75,5 mm x 25,5 mm x 4 mm, model 10000168, lote (batch) JI125176

Figure 13 – TOAPS Chip C (IPQ).

4.1.1 Flow rate determined 'outside' the chip at IPQ

The following figure presents the test setup used for the flow test at IPQ using the gravimetric method.

Figure 14 – Gravimetric flow setup.

The flow is generated by a programmable syringe pump with flow measurement range from 2 pl/min to 500 ml/min ($\pm <0,35\%$, 0,1% reproducibility, Nexus 3000 infuse/withdraw system, Chemyx Precision Syringe Pumps. PE tube of 1,26 mm (0,05") inner diameter was used in the flow path.

The following figure presents the test setup used for the flow test at IPQ using the front track method.

Figure 15 – Front track flow setup.

A high-resolution Alvium 1800 U-1240 camera with a resolution of 12 MP and a Qioptic Optem 7:1 telecentric zoom lens was used. The camera is connected to a computer and uses Python as the programming language that identifies the meniscus and calculates its position. The flow is generated by a programmable syringe pump with a flow measurement range from 2 $\mu\text{l}/\text{min}$ to 500 ml/min ($\pm <0,35\%$, 0,1% reproducibility, Nexus 3000 infuse/withdraw system, Chemyx Precision Syringe Pumps. For the measurements, a PE tube of 1,26 mm (0,05 in) inner diameter was used.

The following table shows the experimental results obtained for the measurements of flow rate using the gravimetric method for Chip A and Chip C.

Table 3 – Results of the gravimetric flow measurements at IPQ (Chip A and Chip C).

Chip	Set Flow (mL/h)	Measured Flow (mL/h)	Error (%)	U (%)
A	0,01	0,0099	1,0	5,0
	0,1	0,0983	1,7	3,8
	1	0,9907	0,93	0,19
C	0,01	0,0069	31,0	5,0
	0,1	0,097	2,6	3,4
	1	1,017	-1,7	3,0

The following table shows the experimental results obtained for the measurements of flow rate using the front tracking method for Chip A and Chip C.

Table 4 – Results of the front tracking measurements at IPQ (Chip A and Chip C).

Chip	Set Flow (mL/h)	Measured Flow (mL/h)	Error (%)	U (%)
A	0,01	0,0095	5,3	3,7
	0,1	0,0967	3,4	2,8
	1	0,9819	1,8	6,2
C	0,01	-0,0033	-403,0	43,0
	0,1	0,0996	0,5	1,9
	1	1,0259	-2,5	4,0

4.1.2 Flow resistivity determined at CETIAT

The following figure presents the test setup used for the flow resistivity test.

Figure 16 – Schematic of the flow resistivity test setup. (F) flow sensor, (P) pressure sensor, (O) outlet of the microfluidic chip.

The following picture shows photographs of the test setup.

Figure 17 – Photographs of the test setup.

The test setup used the following equipment (letters in brackets refers to the schematic in the schematic above):

- Pressure controller: Elveflow OB1 MkII, used on its 0 to 200 mbar or 0 to 2000 mbar channels. The 0 to 200 mbar channel, used for this test, has been calibrated before the test and used for the pressure readings.
- Flow sensor:
 - Bronkhorst ML120 (83 $\mu\text{l}/\text{min}$ full range, readings acquired using the FlowPlot software)
 - Elveflow MFS 2 (7 $\mu\text{l}/\text{min}$ full range, reading acquired using the ESI software)
- Thermo-hygro-barometer ROTRONIC LOG-HC2-P1 / HC2-C05 for recording of temperature, humidity, and ambient pressure at the device under test location.

All instruments were calibrated on their full range, and by traceability to national standard at CETIAT laboratory or by ISO17025 accredited laboratories.

The fluid used for the tests was ultra-pure degassed water (conductivity inferior to 0,06 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$, filtered at 0,2 μm).

All pipes used to make the fluidic connection between the different items of the setup, from the pressure controller to the device under test, were stainless steel 1/16" pipes.

At the inlet port of the device under test, a luer male to threaded Upchurch adapter (reference P-683-01), with an additional threaded female-female Upchurch elbow, has been used to connect the fluidic path to the device under test, as shown in the next figure.

Figure 18 – Adapter used to connect the fluidic setup to the microfluidic chip.

The reference of three assembly components (from the device under test to the 1/16" stainless steel pipe) are:

- Luer male to threaded Upchurch adapter (reference P-683-01)
- Threaded female-female Upchurch 1/16" OD PEEK elbow (reference P-430)
- Upchurch Flangeless Nut for 1/16" OD (reference P-235)

4.1.3 Internal volume determination at IPQ

The volume of the two chips were determined using the gravimetric method, a XP205 Mettler balance with 0,01 mg resolution was used. The reference liquid is ultrapure water. The liquid temperature was measure with a PT100 sensor of 0,01 °C resolution.

The following table shows the experimental results obtained for the measurements of volume rate using the gravimetric method for Chip A and Chip C. The volume values given in Table 5 represent the average of 10 repeated measurements.

Table 5 – Results of the volume determination at IPQ (Chip A and Chip C).

Gravimetric method			
Chip	Channel	Volume (mL)	U (mL)
A	1	0,00390	0,00010
	8	0,00426	0,00014
C	1	0,00387	0,00016
	13	0,00385	0,00007

The volume of the channels measured in the TOPAS chips is similar.

4.2 PDMS microfluidic chip

IPQ performed the volume and flow measurements on 3 different chips, two made of Topas provided by Microfluidic ChipShop and one of PDMS, mainly:

- a) Chip – 1 channel with two 0,9 mm inlet holes, Material: PDMS, Dimensions: 40 x 10 mm², manufactured by INESC MN.

Figure 19 – PDMS Chip

4.2.1 Flow rate determined ‘outside’ the chip at IPQ

The following measurements were carried out at IPQ with the same test setup as described in section 4.1.1.

The following table shows the experimental results obtained for the measurements of flow rate using the gravimetric method for the PDMS chip.

Table 6 – Results of the gravimetric flow measurements at IPQ (PDMS Chip).

Chip	Set Flow (mL/h)	Measured Flow (mL/h)	Error (%)	U (%)
PDMS	0,001	0,00092	8,0	23,0
	0,1	0,0993	0,7	4,6
	0,1	0,0993	0,7	2,5
	1	0,9945	0,55	2,4
	1	0,9907	0,93	0,19

The following table shows the experimental results obtained for the measurements of flow rate using the front tracking method for the PDMS chip.

Table 7 – Results of the front tracking flow measurements at IPQ (PDMS Chip).

Chip	Set Flow (mL/h)	Measured Flow (mL/h)	Error (%)	U (%)
PDMS	0,001	-0,0014	-171,0	14,0
	0,01	0,0113	-11,8	3,3
	0,1	0,0961	4,0	2,6
	1	1,0257	-2,5	4,0

4.2.2 Internal volume determination at IPQ

The volume of the two chips were determined using the gravimetric method, a XP205 Mettler balance with 0,01 mg resolution was used. The reference liquid is ultrapure water. The liquid temperature was measure with a PT100 sensor of 0,01 °C resolution.

The following table shows the experimental results obtained for the measurements of volume rate using the gravimetric method for the PDMS chip. The volume value given in Table 8 represents the average of 10 repeated measurements.

Table 8 – Results of the volume determination at IPQ (PDMS Chip).

Gravimetric method			
Chip	Channel	Volume (mL)	U (mL)
PDMS	1	0,00277	0,00004

4.3 Microfluidic pump

IPQ performed flow measurements with a microfluidic pump which was developed and fabricated by INESC MN within the EMPIR project 18HLT08 Metrology for Drug Delivery ([18HLT08 MeDD II](#)). The operating principle of the pump is described in more detail in the MeDD2 Report A3.2.5 ([Deliverable D5](#)).

Figure 20 – Microfluidic pump flow test using front track method.

- A – Microfluidic pump
- B – Power source
- C – Tubes BTPE 90
- D – capillary tube

E – Hight resolution camara

F – Paper for light diffusion and LED

G – Computer programme

4.3.1 Flow rate determined at IPQ

As shown in Figure 20, due to the low flow rates of the pump (close to 0,005 mL/h), the flow determination of the microfluidic pump was carried using the front track method.

The following table shows the experimental results obtained for the measurements of volume rate using the front track method.

Table 9 – Results of the front track flow measurements at IPQ (microfluidic pump).

	Set Flow (mL/h)	Measured Flow (mL/h)	Error (%)	U (%)
Microfluidic pump	0,005	0,005041235	-0,8	4,8

5 References

- [1] Christopher Vega-Sánchez, Chiara Neto, Pressure Drop Measurements in Microfluidic Devices: A Review on the Accurate Quantification of Interfacial Slip, *Advanced Materials Interfaces*, Volume 9, Issue 5, February 14, 2022
- [2] IEC 60601-2-24:2012 - Medical electrical equipment - Part 2-24: Particular requirements for the basic safety and essential performance of infusion pumps and controllers
- [3] AAMI TIR 101:2021 - Fluid delivery performance testing for infusion pumps
- [4] Bissig, H., Batista, E. et al. (2015), Primary standards for measuring flow rates from 100 nl/min to 1 ml/min – gravimetric principle, *Biomedical Engineering*, 60 (4): 301-316
- [5] ISO 3696:1987 - Water for analytical laboratory use - Specification and test methods
- [6] 18HLT08 MeDDII, Deliverable 1 (A1.2.5), www.drugmetrology.com
- [7] Batista, E. Uncertainty calculations in optical methods used for micro flow measurement, *Measurement: Sensors* 18 (2021) 100155
- [8] Batista, E., Godinho, I., Martins, R., Mendes, R., Robarts, J., (2020), Development of an experimental setup for microflow measurement using interferometry, *Flow Measurement and Instrumentation*, vol. 75
- [9] Batista, E., Furtado, A., Pereira, J. & Godinho, I., (2021), Uncertainty calculation in nanoflow measurements using interferometry, *Advanced Mathematical and Computational Tools in Metrology and Testing XII* vol.12, World Scientific
- [10] ISO 4787:2022 Laboratory glass and plastic ware - Volumetric instruments - Methods for testing of capacity and for use
- [11] A Picard, R S Davis, M Glaser and K Fujii, Revised formula for the density of moistair (CIPM-2007), *Metrologia* 45 (2008) 149–155
- [12] Tanaka, M., Girard, G., Davis, R., Peuto, Bignell, N., (2001), Recommended table for the density of water between 0 °C and 40 °C based on recent experimental reports, *Metrologia*, 38:301-309
- [13] EURAMET calibration guide no.19 - Guidelines on the determination of uncertainty in gravimetric volume calibration, version 3.0 (09/2018)
- [14] Thurow, K., Krüger, T., and Stoll, N., (2009), An optical approach for the determination of droplet volumes in nanodispensing, *Journal of Automated Methods and Management in Chemistry*, 2009,198732
- [15] Batista, Elsa, PhD Thesis in Mechanical Engineering, Innovative contributions on calibration methodologies towards reliable microflow measurements, FCT/UNL, 2022.
- [16] Monge R, Groenesteijn J, Alveringh D, Wiegerink R J, Lötters J and Fernandez L J, 2017, SU–8 micro coriolis mass flow sensor, *Sensors Actuators* 241 744–9
- [17] Sparks D, Smith R, Massoud-Ansari S and Najafi N, 2004, Coriolis mass flow, density and temperature sensing with a single vacuum sealed mems chip, *Solid-State Sensor, Actuator and Microsystems Workshop*, Hilton Head Island, South Carolina Citeseer 4
- [18] Belardinelli P, Hauzer L M F R, Šiškins M, Ghatkesar M K and Alijani F, 2018, Modal analysis for density and anisotropic elasticity identification of adsorbates on microcantilevers, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* 113 143102
- [19] Ghatkesar M K, Rakhmatullina E, Lang H-P, Gerber C, Hegner M and Braun T, 2008, Multi-parameter microcantilever sensor for comprehensive characterization of Newtonian fluids, *Sensors Actuators* 135 133–8
- [20] Burg T P and Manalis S R, 2003, Suspended microchannel resonators for biomolecular detection, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* 83 2698–700

- [21] S B Puneeth, M B Kulkarni and S Goel, 2021, Microfluidic viscometers for biochemical and biomedical applications: A review, Eng. Res. Express 3, 022003, <https://doi.org/10.1088/2631-8695/abfd47>
- [22] Del Giudice F, 2022, Review of Microfluidic Devices for Rheological Characterisation, Micromachines 13, 167; <https://doi.org/10.3390/mi13020167>
- [23] F. Purr, M. Bassu, R. D. Lowe, B. Thürmann, A. Dietzel and T. P. Burg, 2017, Asymmetric nanofluidic grating detector for differential refractive index measurement and biosensing, Lab Chip 17, 4265, <https://doi.org/10.1039/c7lc00929a>
- [24] Silverio, V., & Cardoso, S. (2021). Lab-on-a-chip: Systems integration at the microscale. In Drug Delivery Devices and Therapeutic Systems (pp. 63–87). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-819838-4.00020-1>
- [25] Elsa Batista, João A. Sousa, Miguel Álvares, Joana Afonso, Rui F. Martins, Application of the front tracking method in micro flow measuring devices, Measurement: Sensors, Volume 23, 2022, 100397, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.measen.2022.100397>
- [26] Elsa Batista, João A. Sousa, Miguel Álvares, Joana Afonso, Rui F. Martins, Development of an experimental setup for micro flow measurement using the front tracking method, Measurement: Sensors, Volume 18, 2021, 100152, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.measen.2021.100152>